

Received 24 July 2025, accepted 18 August 2025, date of publication 25 August 2025, date of current version 29 August 2025.

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3602292

APPLIED RESEARCH

A Knowledge-Driven Approach to Threat Validation and Security Reasoning in Modular Systems

LAURA PANDOLFO¹, (Member, IEEE), GIORGIO CORONA¹,
DARIO GUIDOTTI¹, (Member, IEEE), AND LUCA PULINA¹, (Member, IEEE)

DUMAS, University of Sassari, 07100 Sassari, Italy

Corresponding author: Laura Pandolfo (lpandolfo@uniss.it)

This work was supported by the European Union's (EU) Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under project SECURED "Scaling Up Secure Processing, Anonymization and Generation of Health Data for EU Cross Border Collaborative Research and Innovation," Grant Agreement No. 101095717.

ABSTRACT Modular systems are increasingly employed in critical application domains such as healthcare, smart cities, and Industry 4.0 platforms, where dynamic integration of components poses substantial challenges in ensuring consistent and secure operation. Validating system configurations against known vulnerabilities and threats requires formal, scalable, and explainable approaches. This paper presents a knowledge-driven framework designed to support the validation of modular systems with respect to cybersecurity threats and consistency constraints. Our approach leverages domain-specific ontologies built from well-established threat and vulnerability taxonomies and encodes inference rules to automatically detect potential threats and recommend mitigation strategies. The framework, which includes a reasoning engine and a user-friendly graphical interface providing transparent and traceable explanations for each identified threat, is applied to a modular platform for privacy-preserving, decentralized processing of health data across European institutions. While this composable architecture enables multiple stakeholders to develop, deploy, and maintain specialised components fostering scalability and flexibility, it also introduces critical risks related to architectural coherence and security enforcement. In this context, our framework ensures a human-interpretable assessment of the system's security posture, even in the presence of heterogeneous technologies and policies.

INDEX TERMS Cybersecurity, modular systems, threat modeling, ontology-based reasoning, explainable AI.

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing complexity, modularity, and interconnectivity of digital infrastructures have considerably amplified their exposure to cybersecurity threats. This trend is particularly concerning in data-sensitive domains such as healthcare, where digital platforms must ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of sensitive patient information and analytics workflows. As systems become more decentralised and composed of independently developed modules, ensuring their secure and coherent integration becomes a

pressing challenge [1], [2]. To address these needs, the SECURED project – funded under the Horizon Europe programme – has introduced the *Innohub*, a modular platform for privacy-preserving and decentralised processing of health data across European institutions [3]. The platform adopts a composable architecture, enabling multiple stakeholders to develop, deploy, and maintain specialised components. While this design fosters scalability and flexibility, it also introduces critical risks in terms of architectural coherence and security enforcement. The heterogeneity of technologies, communication standards, and security policies across modules poses a significant challenge to achieving a unified and explainable assessment of the system's overall security.

The associate editor coordinating the review of this manuscript and approving it for publication was Alba Amato¹.

Conventional validation approaches, which are typically manual or informal, prove inadequate in this context. Heterogeneity across modules can result in misalignments in threat modelling, inconsistent application of mitigation strategies, or undetected propagation paths for vulnerabilities. Without formal guarantees of compliance and coherence, the platform may exhibit latent risks that are difficult to detect and address post-deployment. To overcome these limitations, there is a growing need for machine-readable, formally grounded representations of both system architectures and cybersecurity knowledge. Ontology-based approaches offer a principled solution: they provide structured, extensible models capable of capturing complex relationships between components, threats, vulnerabilities, and countermeasures [4], [5]. When combined with automated reasoning mechanisms, these semantic representations enable proactive verification of security properties and consistency constraints, supporting both local and global assurance. Modular verification of systems using automated reasoning techniques is commonly adopted – see [6], [7], [8].

In this paper, we introduce a knowledge-driven framework for validating modular systems with respect to cybersecurity threats and structural consistency. The framework is designed to support both proactive risk identification and cross-module compliance checking, and is intended for use by both system architects, responsible for global security assurance, and individual module providers, who need to validate their components within a shared infrastructure. The proposed knowledge base is composed of two main parts: one describing the system architecture and components, and the other capturing risks, attacks, vulnerabilities, and mitigation strategies. These two parts are linked through a set of formal inference rules, resulting in an integrated Knowledge Graph (KG) that supports both automated reasoning and human-understandable threat assessments. While the framework has been instantiated for the *Innohub* platform, it is inherently generalisable by replacing the ontology that models the system architecture, the same reasoning and validation mechanisms can be applied to other modular infrastructures in domains such as Industry 4.0, cyber-physical systems, or critical infrastructure monitoring.

To facilitate practical adoption, we implemented the *Risk Manager* tool with a Graphical User Interface (GUI) that allows designers and system architects to query the knowledge base visually, explore potential threat scenarios, and review validation results in an explainable and user-friendly manner.

The main contributions of this work are as follows:

- The definition of a modular ontology representing architectural components alongside cybersecurity threats, vulnerabilities, and mitigations.
- The integration of all system knowledge into a unified KG, enabling semantic querying and traceable threat analysis.

- The implementation of a reasoning layer based on rules that automates threat detection and consistency verification.
- The development of a GUI-based tool to support explainable validation and visualisation of system-wide security risks.

We evaluated the framework in representative configurations of the *Innohub* platform, demonstrating its effectiveness in identifying threats and enforcing compliance with minimal overhead. The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. In Section II, we provide the background on ontology-based modelling and established threat modelling methodologies, while Section III reviews the most relevant related work. Section IV presents the modelling of system architecture and threats, detailing the development of our knowledge base and the formulation of reasoning rules. Section V is dedicated to the architecture of the supporting tool and its GUI. Section VI discusses the results of the evaluation, focussing on the correctness and expressiveness of the proposed ontology, the effectiveness of the reasoning mechanisms, and the usability of the GUI. Finally, Section VII concludes the paper and outlines the directions for future work.

II. BACKGROUND

This section presents the foundational concepts that guide our proposed framework, with a focus on semantic modelling and automated threat analysis. We first introduce ontological representations and reasoning techniques, then examine mainstream threat modelling methodologies and their limitations in the context of modular system validation.

A. MODELLING WITH ONTOLOGIES

Ontologies provide a formal and machine-readable representation of domain knowledge, enabling structured reasoning over complex interrelationships among entities [9]. In cybersecurity, ontologies have been increasingly adopted to model threats, vulnerabilities, and system components in a unified semantic framework [10].

An ontology comprises a vocabulary of concepts (classes), specific instances (individuals), and relations (properties) among them, which can be either object properties (linking instances to other instances) or data properties (linking instances to data values). Ontologies are typically expressed in the Web Ontology Language (OWL) [11], [12], which is grounded in Description Logics (DL) [13], a family of formal knowledge representation languages that support logical reasoning.

In this formalism, abstract security concepts are represented using DL axioms. Please note that the following axioms are illustrative examples from common security ontologies and are not necessarily used in our model. For space reasons, we abbreviate *vulnerability* as `Vuln`, *critical vulnerability* as `CriticalVuln`, *exploits vulnerability* as `exploitsVuln`, and *has severity level* as `hasSeverity`.

For example:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Threat} &\sqsubseteq \text{SecurityEvent} \\ \text{Vuln} &\sqsubseteq \text{SecurityWeakness} \end{aligned}$$

These statements specify subclass relationships, asserting that every instance of `Threat` is a `SecurityEvent`, and every `Vuln` is a type of `SecurityWeakness`. Individuals instantiate these classes, such as:

$$\text{SQLInjection} : \text{Threat}$$

This indicates that `SQLInjection` is an instance of the class `Threat`.

Properties define relationships between entities. For instance, object properties such as `exploitsVuln` link a `Threat` to a `Vuln`, while data properties like `hasSeverity` associate vulnerabilities with severity metrics. Logical restrictions further refine classes; for example, critical vulnerabilities can be defined as:

$$\text{CriticalVuln} \equiv \text{Vuln} \sqcap \text{hasSeverity}.\{\text{"Critical"}\}$$

This enforces that `CriticalVuln` is exactly the set of vulnerabilities with the severity level `"Critical"`.

The result of populating an ontology with individuals and their relationships generates a knowledge graph [14], which represents the instance-level data over which reasoning and querying can be performed. This KG supports semantic interoperability and enables dynamic risk assessments across modular systems.

To extract meaningful insights from the KG, we use SPARQL [15], [16], which is the standard language for querying semantic data. For instance, the following query retrieves all threats with severity `"Critical"`:

```
SELECT ?t WHERE {
  ?t rdf:type sec:Threat;
  :hasSeverity "Critical" .
}
```

Such queries allow system users to identify critical issues, trace component vulnerabilities, or generate compliance reports programmatically.

The formal structure of the ontologies allows automated reasoning using DL reasoners such as Pellet [17], HermiT [18], and FaCT++ [19], which can: *i*) classify threat types into taxonomies; *ii*) detect inconsistencies in the ontology; *iii*) infer attack dependencies and propagation paths.

However, OWL alone is not expressive enough for complex logical conditions. To address this, the Semantic Web Rule Language (SWRL) [20] extends OWL by introducing Horn-like rules [21], [22]. For instance:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Vuln}(?v) \wedge \text{hasSeverity}(?v, \text{"Critical"}) \wedge \\ &\text{exploitsVuln}(?t, ?v) \rightarrow \text{HighRiskThreat}(?t) \end{aligned}$$

This rule states that if a threat exploits a critical vulnerability, it should be inferred as a high-risk threat. Such rules enhance

semantic reasoning by enabling the dynamic classification of threats based on contextual information, which can support higher-level security analysis and decision-making.

B. THREAT MODELLING METHODOLOGIES

Threat modelling is a fundamental process in cybersecurity, which enables organisations to systematically identify and mitigate potential threats to their systems [23]. Although definitions may vary across application domains, it is generally understood as a structured approach for identifying, assessing, and prioritising threats that may compromise the confidentiality, integrity, or availability of digital systems. The advantages of adopting a threat modelling process include the ability to proactively rank risks throughout the system lifecycle and to focus mitigation efforts where they are most needed. Moreover, its iterative nature supports continuous adaptation to evolving threats [24].

A cybersecurity threat can be described as any potential or actual event that exploits vulnerabilities in a system, potentially leading to unauthorised access, data loss, service disruption, or system compromise [25]. Threats may originate from a wide range of sources, such as external attackers, malicious insiders, accidental errors, or environmental factors. To systematically manage this complexity, several methodologies have been proposed to guide threat modelling activities, supporting analysts in identifying assets, defining security perimeters, understanding potential attackers and their capabilities, and prioritising threats based on risk analysis [26], [27].

One of the earliest and most widely adopted frameworks is STRIDE, developed by Microsoft. It categorises threats into six types: Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denial of Service, and Elevation of Privileges. STRIDE is typically applied using Data Flow Diagrams (DFDs) to visualise how data moves through a system and where security threats might emerge. Microsoft's Threat Modeling Tool (TMT) [28] supports this approach by automatically identifying potential threats based on software architecture and suggesting mitigation strategies.

Building on the need for visual and scenario-based representations, Attack Trees [29] were introduced as a hierarchical method for decomposing attack goals into sequences of exploitable actions. This structure helps analysts reason about attack feasibility and coverage, but also requires significant domain knowledge to be used effectively.

As threat modelling evolved to encompass business risk and operational concerns, methodologies such as Process for Attack Simulation and Threat Analysis (PASTA) [30] emerged. PASTA integrates technical and business perspectives across seven stages, including threat and vulnerability analysis, attack simulation, and business impact assessment. This layered approach allows for aligning security decisions with organisational priorities and regulatory constraints.

Other models, like Trike [27], shift the focus from categorising threats to maintaining security requirements within

acceptable risk thresholds. Trike defines a set of security goals and uses stakeholder-defined risk models to guide the evaluation of threat impacts, facilitating customisation to specific domains.

To address the challenges of scalability and agile software development, Visual, Agile, and Simple Threat Modelling (VAST) [31] proposes a dual-model approach: application threat models focus on software components, while operational threat models evaluate infrastructure. Its integration with DevOps pipelines and automation capabilities make it suitable for large-scale systems and continuous delivery environments.

Complementing these approaches is the Operationally Critical Threat, Asset, and Vulnerability Evaluation (OCTAVE) framework [32], which adopts a self-directed, risk-based methodology focusing on organisational context and asset criticality. It is particularly used in enterprise and government settings where operational resilience is paramount.

To bring quantitative metrics into the process, the DREAD model [33] introduces five evaluation dimensions—Damage Potential, Reproducibility, Exploitability, Affected Users, and Discoverability—each contributing to an overall risk score. Despite its practicality, DREAD has seen a decline in adoption due to inconsistencies in scoring between evaluators.

Specialised methodologies have also emerged to address privacy-centric concerns. LINDDUN [34] is designed to identify privacy threats across seven categories, such as Linkability, Identifiability, and Non-compliance. It provides structured support for applications dealing with sensitive personal data and ensures compliance with regulations like the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

While these methodologies differ in scope and perspective, most share the limitation of relying heavily on manual effort and static representations. In response to the growing complexity of systems and the dynamic nature of threats, ontology-based approaches have been proposed [26]. These methods leverage formal representations of knowledge to describe systems, threat patterns, and mitigation strategies in a machine-interpretable way. One of their key strengths is the ability to support automated reasoning, enabling the inference of new security knowledge (e.g., vulnerability propagation, policy violations) from explicitly stated facts.

To remain effective, ontology-based threat models must be integrated with real-world threat intelligence external sources. By aligning ontology-based models with these repositories, threat modelling systems can dynamically adapt to new cybersecurity challenges. Several databases and frameworks provide structured information on known threats, vulnerabilities, and attack patterns, including:

- Common Attack Pattern Enumeration and Classification (CAPEC).¹ A publicly available database maintained by MITRE that provides a comprehensive collection of common attack patterns. CAPEC helps security analysts

understand how adversaries exploit vulnerabilities and devise mitigation strategies.

- Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE).² Also maintained by MITRE, CWE is a community-developed list of software and hardware weaknesses that can lead to security vulnerabilities. It provides a structured taxonomy of weaknesses that developers and security professionals can use to identify and mitigate security flaws.
- Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE).³ Managed by MITRE in collaboration with National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), the CVE database catalogues publicly disclosed cybersecurity vulnerabilities. Each CVE entry contains detailed information on known security issues, affected products, and available mitigation techniques.
- Common Platform Enumeration (CPE).⁴ A structured naming scheme for IT systems, platforms, and applications maintained by NIST. CPE allows security professionals to match specific software and hardware components with known vulnerabilities in the CVE database.

In line with this shift toward automation, recent tools like AutoSEC [35] have begun combining ontological reasoning with rule engines, KGs, and even machine learning to dynamically identify security threats and evaluate system configurations. These technologies aim to minimise human effort, increase consistency, and support real-time threat assessment in modular, fast-evolving architectures.

III. RELATED WORK

Ontology-based threat modelling has gained increasing attention due to its ability to formalise security concepts and automate the threat modelling process. Several frameworks have been proposed in the literature, each with its specific focus and limitations. One of the most recognised efforts is the Ontology-driven Threat Modelling (OdTM) by OWASP [36]. This framework aims to automate threat modelling by building a *Base Threat Model*, an OWL ontology that encapsulates Information and Communication Technology (ICT) infrastructure components, threats, mitigations, and relationships. The framework also supports domain-specific extensions to enhance adaptability across different cybersecurity contexts. Similarly, in [37] the authors propose an ontology-driven approach tailored for cloud environments, structuring security components to facilitate threat identification. However, their model relies heavily on well-known vulnerabilities, limiting its ability to predict emerging threats.

Other contributions, such as [10], attempt to improve automation in threat modelling by addressing domain knowledge gaps and mismatched granularity. However, the

²<https://cwe.mitre.org/>

³<https://www.cve.org/>

⁴<https://cpe.mitre.org/about/>

¹<https://capec.mitre.org/>

framework remains constrained to software-related threats and relies primarily on known system vulnerabilities. In [38], the authors simulate the impact of an informed incident (a materialised threat) on corporate assets through a threat ontology. The ontology describes both cyber and physical threats, such as fires and natural disasters, following Landwehr's taxonomy [39].

The ThreMA approach [26] proposes a standard meta-model to describe a complete ICT infrastructure, establishing a formal and common vocabulary for all involved parties. Threats are categorised and formalised within the designed ontology based on common threat databases. Additionally, a well-defined set of inference rules describes threat modelling logic and maps infrastructure components to threats using ontology reasoners. The ThreMA ontology metamodel consists of three sub-ontologies: the ICT sub-ontology for modelling the infrastructure, the Data Flow sub-ontology for representing DFD, and the threat sub-ontology for characterising threats. These sub-ontologies are connected by relationships, and the threat modelling logic is expressed through inference rules. The ThreMA ontology is developed using Protégé [40] and employs OWL 2 [41] as its ontology description language, with SWRL used for specifying inference rules.

Although ThreMA offers a structured and automated approach to threat modelling, it exhibits certain limitations, particularly the lack of connections between several ontology classes, which can affect the efficiency and completeness of reasoning processes. Our work builds upon a similar ontology-driven methodology, while addressing these shortcomings to improve both the expressiveness of the model and the effectiveness of inference. Furthermore, whereas ThreMA relies primarily on the CAPEC and CWE datasets, our approach extends this foundation by also incorporating the complete CVE database.

Summarising, most literature approaches focus on specific vertical domains, making them hard to reuse in different contexts. They also lack standard representations of models and data used in various process stages. Inference rules supporting reasoning during threat identification are generally tailored to specific vulnerabilities and attacks. Furthermore, existing approaches automate only part of the threat modelling process, requiring human interaction to define threats and relying on external tools in a non-integrated manner.

IV. ONTOLOGY MODELLING OF SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND THREATS

The design of a structured and expressive ontology is a key phase in the development of the framework. In order to support automated reasoning over both the *Innohub* system architecture and its associated cybersecurity threats, we developed an integrated model that captures structural, behavioural, and risk-related aspects of the platform.

This section details the process adopted to build the ontology, following a multi-phase methodology comprising

requirements elicitation, conceptual modelling, formal construction, and evaluation. The ontology itself is organised into two interrelated modules: the *Innohub sub-ontology*, which formalises the architecture of the system, and the *threat sub-ontology*, which represents known vulnerabilities, attack patterns, and their relations.

In addition, we introduce a set of rule-based axioms expressed in SWRL, which enrich the ontology with inference capabilities. These rules allow the framework to detect architectural inconsistencies, validate access policies, and establish dynamic associations between threats and system components.

The subsections that follow describe each of these elements in detail.

A. ONTOLOGY DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The design of the ontology plays a central role in ensuring the framework effectively captures the complexities of the *Innohub* architecture along with its associated cybersecurity threats. Our development process took inspiration from the ontology-driven metamodel proposed in [26]. Building on this foundation, we adopted a streamlined design, employing two distinct but interconnected sub-ontologies: one to model the structural and behavioural aspects of the *Innohub* system, and another to represent the range of threats, vulnerabilities, and mitigation strategies relevant to the platform.

The development of the ontology followed a structured methodology comprising four key phases: *a*: Requirements identification, *b*: Modelling, *c*: Construction, and *d*: Evaluation.

1) REQUIREMENTS IDENTIFICATION

The initial phase of ontology development focused on defining its motivation, competency questions (CQs), and functional requirements. The primary objective is to formally model the *Innohub* framework and its associated threats to support automated reasoning for consistency and security verification. The CQs helped delimit the scope of the ontology and ensured its capacity to answer critical queries concerning infrastructure elements, their interactions, and associated risks. Examples include:

- CQ1: What are the core components of the *Innohub* framework?
- CQ2: How do components interact within the infrastructure?
- CQ3: Which security threats affect specific components?
- CQ4: How do these threats impact security properties?
- CQ5: Can the system retrieve threats classified with “*Very High*” severity?

The functional requirements establish the core modelling constraints, properties, and behaviours necessary for effective security validation. Key requirements include: (i) representation of structural elements, including computing units, storage, protocols, access control, and interdependencies; (ii) integration of established threat taxonomies such as

CAPEC, CWE, and CVE; (iii) explicit links between system components and threats to identify vulnerabilities; (iv) support for automated reasoning to infer knowledge and verify constraints; (v) use of SWRL rules to detect violations and suggest mitigations; (vi) mechanisms for assessing threat impact and prioritising risks; (vii) extensibility to incorporate new threats, components, and policies; and (viii) ability to answer predefined competency questions regarding threats, vulnerabilities, and compliance. By aligning with these requirements, the ontology supports the formal analysis of *Innohub*'s security posture and contributes to the detection of potential risks through automated, explainable reasoning.

2) MODELLING

The ontology is structured into two main sub-ontologies: the *Innohub sub-ontology*, which models the architecture of the target system, and the *threat sub-ontology*, which captures cybersecurity threats. The former describes key infrastructure components, including computing resources, data management, communication protocols, and access control strategies, along with their interrelations. These formalised relationships enable automated reasoning on system consistency and security properties. The threat sub-ontology models categories of threats, vulnerabilities, and attack techniques, drawing from established taxonomies and literature. It links threats to specific system elements to support the identification of vulnerabilities and reasoning over potential risks.

The ontology adopts a modular design to ensure maintainability and scalability, allowing each sub-ontology to evolve independently while preserving integrity. Concrete instances represent real system components and known threats, supporting risk analysis and security verification over time.

3) CONSTRUCTION

This phase focuses on formally implementing the ontology based on the conceptual model defined earlier. The ontology is developed using Protégé [39] and Owlready2 [42], two widely used tools for ontology modelling and reasoning. Ontology construction includes iterative validation to refine relationships and optimise reasoning performance, ensuring accurate representation of the system and its security aspects. The ontology uses DL expressivity $\mathcal{SOLIF}(\mathcal{D})$, which balances expressivity and computational efficiency [13]. This enables complex class definitions, role hierarchies, inverse and functional properties, and datatype restrictions, supporting robust reasoning.

Platform components and security threats are instantiated within the ontology, each with specific attributes and relationships reflecting the system's architecture. The threat ontology incorporates CAPEC, CWE and CVE classifications to represent attack techniques, vulnerabilities, and impacts. In addition, we have also instantiated the hardware and software specifications of the platform using the CPE

TABLE 1. Ontology metrics.

Metric	Count
Total axioms	58,555
Logical axioms	49,667
Declaration axioms	3,722
Classes	33
Object properties	26
Data properties	27
Individuals	3,638

standard, enabling precise linking between system components and known vulnerabilities. Relationships between threats and system elements are formalised via SWRL rules, which define conditions to identify vulnerabilities and detect inconsistencies. Automated reasoners process these rules to infer knowledge, verify threat-component links and highlight risks.

A quantitative summary of the ontology is presented in Table 1, reporting the number of axioms, classes, properties, and individuals.⁵

4) EVALUATION

The final phase is dedicated to the evaluation in order to assess the ontology's correctness, completeness, and effectiveness in supporting the verification module's objectives. This process involves multiple validation techniques to ensure that the ontology accurately represents the system architecture and its associated threats while enabling meaningful security analysis. Consistency checking is carried out using automated reasoners to verify the logical soundness of class hierarchies, relationships, and constraints. These checks identify potential inconsistencies, such as contradictory classifications or unintended logical inferences. Additionally, reasoning mechanisms validate the application of SWRL rules to confirm that security constraints and threat conditions are correctly inferred within the ontology's framework. In Section VI-A we provide a detailed evaluation of the ontology.

B. INNOHUB SUB-ONTOLOGY

The *Innohub sub-ontology* models the structural and functional components of the platform. Its development was guided by the detailed specifications of each individual module, with direct contributions from the developers responsible for their implementation.

This part of the ontology defines six core classes: *Back_end*, *Development_libraries*, *Front_end*, *Knowledge_base*, *Services*, and *Tools*. Their interrelations are shown in Figure 1, in which classes and subclasses are shown in green, while individuals are represented in blue. Black dashed arrows denote object

⁵The ontology is openly available under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license on GitHub at: https://github.com/AIMet-Lab/SECURED-Framework-Verification/blob/main/secured_ontology_v0.7.owl

FIGURE 1. Graphical representation of the *Innohub* sub-ontology. Green boxes represent classes (with subclasses where applicable), and blue boxes indicate individuals. The grey database represents external data sources populating the back-end. Black dashed arrows denote object properties; blue dashed arrows represent SWRL rules defining RBAC-based user access to components.

properties representing links between components, enabling inference over security constraints and data flows. The SWRL rule depicted with blue dashed arrows encodes Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) to enforce authentication policies, using built-in functions from the `swrlb:` namespace to perform advanced logical operations and comparisons. For confidentiality reasons related to the project, specific access rules implemented cannot be disclosed. Therefore, the rule shown in the figure has been intentionally generalised to illustrate the mechanism without exposing sensitive information.

The `Back_end` class interfaces with external data sources and captures the computational core of the system, responsible for secure processing and communication. These components rely on Docker and GitLab and expose secure interfaces, including APIs, data adapters, HTTPS, and host ports. Communication mechanisms are tightly coupled with security requirements to ensure encrypted exchanges.

The `Development_libraries` class comprises modules for authentication and security. These integrate with the `orchestrator` and support token validation via identity and access management. They also incorporate privacy-preserving technologies such as homomorphic encryption and secure multiparty computation.

The `Front_end` class is responsible for managing user interactions and represents user-facing components.

It relies on Docker, integrates with the `orchestrator`, and enforces security through Keycloak and SSL. Communication interfaces include HTTPS, host ports, and data adapters, all encoded in the ontology to ensure secure interactions.

The `Knowledge_base` class manages structured repositories such as APIs, databases, and data lakes. It operates with Docker, enforces SSL communication, and interfaces with the `orchestrator`. Subclasses include `API_endpoint`, `Data_lake`, and `Database`, offering granular control over data sources.

The `Services` class groups functionalities into `Platform_services` and `Privacy_preserving_services`, covering anonymisation, bias assessment, legal compliance, synthetic data generation, and unbiasing. All services adhere to defined privacy and security constraints.

Lastly, the `Tools` class encompasses utilities for managing privacy, security, and data. Each tool integrates with the `orchestrator` and supports access control via identity and access management, ensuring secure deployment and usage across the system.

C. THREAT SUB-ONTOLOGY

The *threat sub-ontology* is designed to model cybersecurity threats and integrate them with external threat intelligence sources. This sub-ontology incorporates representations of

FIGURE 2. Graphical representation of the *threat sub-ontology's* classes (in orange) along with their interactions with the *Innohub* components (in green) and the CPE class (in purple). In the diagram, classes appear as boxes containing their related data properties; associated subclasses and object properties are additionally represented. The ontology identifies potential cybersecurity threats through two complementary mechanisms: (i) keyword-based searches using the SWRL `containsIgnoreCase` built-in, which match *Innohub* component specifications with textual descriptions of attacks and vulnerabilities; and (ii) CPE-based mapping of *Innohub's* hardware and software components to CVE-listed vulnerabilities. Both streams populate the *Threat* class. Components are linked to potential threats via the `hasTarget` property (and its inverse `isTargetOf`). Relationships are shown as black dashed arrows when derived from CPE mappings, and as azure dashed arrows when inferred via SWRL reasoning (with the entire reasoning flow shown in azure).

attack patterns (CAPEC), weaknesses (CWE) and vulnerabilities (CVE) to establish a comprehensive threat landscape.

Figure 2 illustrates the hierarchical structure and inter-relations within this sub-ontology. In particular, it provides a visual representation of the ontology's core classes and relationships, highlighting the integration between threats and *Innohub* components. It demonstrates how CAPEC attack patterns, CWE weaknesses, and CVE vulnerabilities are interconnected and mapped to CPE-listed hardware and software. Furthermore, it establishes a direct link between threats and the *SECURED_innohub* architecture, enabling automated threat assessment through reasoning mechanisms.

The *threat sub-ontology* is structured around five main classes:

- The *Threat* class represents specific threats that are linked to components of the *Innohub* platform. Note that the term *threat* is used in a broad sense, encompassing not only actual cybersecurity threats but also related elements such as CWE and CVE entries. A threat instance is defined when an attack technique or vulnerability explicitly targets a system component. Through formal relationships and reasoning mechanisms, these threats are systematically associated with the affected modules,

enabling automated threat analysis and supporting proactive risk mitigation strategies. The identification of threats is governed by rules, as illustrated in Figure 2, which formalise the conditions under which an ontology instance qualifies as a threat based on its relationships to components.

- The CAPEC class represents attack techniques, categorised by methodology and execution domain. Each attack pattern has properties such as abstraction level, likelihood, severity, impact, and mitigation strategies. This class includes a single subclass, `3000_Domain_of_Attack`, which corresponds to CAPEC's hierarchical organization of attack patterns based on execution domain (ID: 3000). This subclass, in turn, is further divided into the following subclasses of attack patterns:
 - `403_Social_Engineering`: attacks exploiting human psychology to manipulate users into performing actions or divulging confidential information.
 - `437_Supply_Chain`: attacks targeting weaknesses in supply chain components, including third-party vendors, hardware, and software dependencies.

- 512_Communications: attacks on communication channels, such as network-based exploits, eavesdropping, and man-in-the-middle attacks.
 - 513_Software: software-focused attacks, including injection techniques, memory corruption, and software misconfiguration exploits.
 - 514_Physical_Security: attacks involving physical access to hardware, tampering, and unauthorized access to secure locations.
 - 515_Hardware: attacks targeting vulnerabilities in hardware components, including firmware exploits and hardware Trojans.
- The *CWE* class is designed to capture a wide spectrum of software and hardware vulnerabilities by organising them into thematically coherent sub-categories. These sub-classes reflect established security taxonomies and are grouped according to key focus areas such as data protection, hardware-specific issues, and software-level weaknesses. In particular, this class includes subdivisions aligned with standards like the CISQ Data Protection schema and the most recent *CWE Top 25* and extensions, covering both hardware (2021) and software (2024) perspectives. The following list details the main sub-classes of the *CWE* class and their respective scopes:
 - *CISQ_Data_Protection*: a set of weaknesses related to secure data management, including improper encryption, insufficient access control, and insecure data storage practices. These vulnerabilities are particularly relevant for compliance with data protection standards such as GDPR and ISO 27001 [43].
 - *HW_2021_Top*: a collection of the most critical hardware security weaknesses identified in 2021, covering issues such as side-channel attacks, firmware vulnerabilities, and unsafe hardware initialization sequences.
 - *HW_2021_extension*: an extension of the *HW_2021_Top* category, including additional hardware security weaknesses. These represent weaknesses identified by the *CWE* team as ranked just outside the *Top 25* threshold, and are suggested for consideration in risk analyses.
 - *SW_2024_Top_25*: a curated list of the top 25 most dangerous software weaknesses identified in 2024, compiled based on their impact, exploitability, and frequency in real-world attacks. This category highlights critical vulnerabilities such as improper input validation, buffer overflows, and deserialization flaws.
 - *SW_2024_extension*: an extension of the *SW_2024_Top_25* list, including additional software weaknesses identified through ongoing security research. These weaknesses often involve newly discovered exploitation techniques or vulnerabilities in emerging software architectures.

TABLE 2. Number of individuals populating key classes in the threat model.

Class	Number of Individuals
CAPEC	559
Social Engineering	111
Supply Chain	89
Communications	194
Software	510
Physical Security	79
Hardware	209
CWE	940
CVE	2095
CISQ Data Protection	89
HW 2021 Top	12
HW 2021 Extension	5
SW 2024 Top 25	25
SW 2024 Extension	15
Threat	724

- The *CVE* class lists specific vulnerabilities affecting system components, each described by Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) severity ratings, affected products, and security implications.
- The *CPE* class represents specific software applications, hardware devices, and operating systems, allowing for precise mapping between vulnerabilities and affected technologies. This class is further divided into three key sub-classes:
 - *Applications*: includes software programs and platforms, such as web applications, databases, and enterprise solutions.
 - *Hardware_devices*: represents physical computing components, such as processors, embedded systems, IoT devices, and network equipment.
 - *Operating_systems*: covers OS-level components and system configurations.

Some of these classes, along with their relational and descriptive properties, were partially imported from the OdTM ontology set [44]. Specifically, they were derived from the OdTM Integrated Model, while their properties were sourced from the OdTM Base Threat Model.

This module of the ontology contains a rich set of individuals distributed across key classes, as you can see in Table 2, which presents the number of individuals populating the main classes of the *threat sub-ontology*. The *CVE* class holds the largest number of instances, reflecting the extensive database of documented vulnerabilities. *CWE* and *CAPEC* classes also include a significant number of instances, demonstrating the classification of software weaknesses and attack techniques. A particularly noteworthy aspect is the *Threat* class, which encompasses 724 individuals, indicating that a substantial number of threats, vulnerabilities, and attack techniques are mapped directly to the system components within the *Innohub* framework. The high number of instances in this class suggests a comprehensive integration of threat intelligence, ensuring that the ontology provides actionable insights for security assessment and response.

The *threat sub-ontology* models the relationships between attack patterns, weaknesses, and vulnerabilities by leveraging properties such as `hasAncestor`, `isAncestorOf`, `peerOf`, `canFollow`, and `canProceed`. These transitive relationships reconstruct the hierarchical structure of attack techniques, clarifying their dependencies and progression in real-world exploitation scenarios. In addition, threat classifications are enriched with data properties, describing abstraction level, impact, likelihood, severity, and recommended mitigation strategies. These structured representations enable automated reasoning mechanisms for identifying and assessing potential security risks.

A key aspect of the *threat sub-ontology* is its explicit semantic alignment with the *Innohub sub-ontology*. This alignment is achieved through the use of relationships such as `hasTarget` and `isTargetOf`, that create direct links between threat entities and infrastructure elements. This integration enables the ontology to serve as a comprehensive and queryable KG that captures both the technical architecture and its associated risk landscape.

To exemplify how threats are formally represented in this ontology, Table 3 presents a structured view of the CAPEC-244 attack pattern. This includes semantic attributes such as affected components, severity, mitigation strategies, and links to related CWE instances. These definitions, while statically modelled here, can later be used to drive automated threat detection and prioritisation processes.

TABLE 3. Example of threat representation related to CAPEC-244.

Attribute	Value
Identifier	CAPEC-244
Ancestors	CAPEC-63, CAPEC-588, CAPEC-242, CAPEC-592, CAPEC-591
Reference to CWE	CWE-83
Targets	Anonymising tool, anonymised data transformation toolset
Impact	Execute unauthorised commands, modify data, bypass protection mechanisms, gain privileges, read data
Severity	High
Scope	Integrity, access control, authentication, non-repudiation, confidentiality
Mitigation	Disable scripting languages, sanitise input, enforce strict encoding, patch software
Description	An attack that exploits browsers interpreting data in URI placeholders, executing malicious scripts upon user interaction.

D. SWRL RULES INTEGRATION

The reasoning mechanism enables verification of both architectural consistency and cybersecurity posture by applying rule-based inference over the structured knowledge base. Reasoning is implemented using SWRL rules and supports the detection of implicit relationships, validation of compliance constraints, and identification of potential vulnerabilities across modular components.

A summary of the SWRL rules and their corresponding effects is reported in Table 4. A first class of rules focuses on access control verification. In particular, *Rule 0* verifies whether a user holds a valid token for accessing a specific component. If the token value matches the required access condition defined for that component, the user is granted access.

The second class of rules (*Rules 1-3*) enables the semantic association between external threat definitions (CAPEC, CWE, CVE) and internal components of the *Innohub* infrastructure. This is achieved by comparing textual descriptions of known threats with the technical specifications of system elements. If a match is found, a semantic link is established, indicating that the component may be affected by the threat. This is formalised via the `hasTarget` property.

Finally, to improve coverage in cases where standard descriptions are insufficient or unavailable, additional rules (*Rules 4-5*) extend the reasoning process to consider alternative metadata fields, such as free-text notes. These rules ensure robustness by capturing less structured threat annotations.

V. TOOL ARCHITECTURE AND USER INTERFACE

To provide end users with an accessible interface for navigating and verifying the system's security model, we developed a GUI-based tool, known as the *Risk Manager*, that enables users to explore the system components, detect associated cybersecurity threats, and verify access control permissions. The tool and installation instructions are publicly accessible.⁶ Acting as an interactive front-end to the KG and reasoning infrastructure, the tool enables users to inspect inferred threat relationships, examine affected components, and retrieve structured vulnerability data, without requiring direct interaction with formal ontology languages or reasoning engines.

Figure 3 illustrates the architecture of the *Risk Manager* tool and its workflow. On the left-hand side, multiple external sources, including vulnerability taxonomies (CAPEC, CWE, CVE), feeds from the NIST National Vulnerability Database (NVD), and internal technical specifications are processed to populate the ontology. Specifically, CAPEC entries populate instances of the `CAPEC` class, CWE entries populate `CWE`, and CVE entries populate `CVE`. The NVD feeds are used to instantiate the `CPE` class, while internal technical specifications are used to populate the *Innohub sub-ontology* classes. These populated classes form a central KG that semantically integrates system architecture, software platforms, and cybersecurity threats. In this context, *Innohub* components interact with `CPE` individuals representing software platforms, which in turn are linked to `CVE` individuals through object properties, establishing relationships between software platforms and known vulnerabilities. Together with

⁶<https://github.com/AIMet-Lab/SECURED-Framework-Verification/blob/main/RiskManager>

TABLE 4. Summary of SWRL rules implemented in the framework.

Rule	Purpose	Formalisation (DL-like Syntax)
Rule 0	RBAC-based access control	$RBAC_token(u, t) \wedge RBAC_rule(c, t) \rightarrow userAccess(u, c)$
Rule 1	CAPEC-component association (description)	$CAPEC(x) \wedge SECURED_innohub(s) \wedge technical_specification(s, d) \wedge hasDescription(x, d') \wedge containsIgnoreCase(d', d) \rightarrow hasTarget(x, s)$
Rule 2	CWE-component association (description)	Same as Rule 1, with CWE instead of CAPEC
Rule 3	CVE-component association (description)	Same as Rule 1, with CVE instead of CAPEC
Rule 4	CAPEC-component association (note field)	$CAPEC(x) \wedge SECURED_innohub(s) \wedge technical_specification(s, d) \wedge note(x, n) \wedge containsIgnoreCase(n, d) \rightarrow hasTarget(x, s)$
Rule 5	CWE-component association (note field)	Same as Rule 4, with CWE instead of CAPEC

FIGURE 3. Architecture of the Risk Manager and its workflow. External sources (e.g., CAPEC, CWE, CVE, NIST feeds, internal technical specifications) are used to populate the ontology and are stored in a knowledge graph that links system components, CPEs, and threats/vulnerabilities. Reasoning is performed via SWRL rules, and results are exposed to the GUI through automated SPARQL queries.

CAPEC and CWE classes, all this information is leveraged by a set of SWRL rules that perform inference to identify and associate cybersecurity threats with specific *Innohub* components. The resulting inferred assertions are stored into the class *Threat* and made accessible to the user-facing GUI through dynamic SPARQL queries. The query results are mapped to interactive GUI elements (such as filters, drop-down menus, and contextual summaries) enabling a guided and explainable exploration of the threat landscape. As shown in Figure 4, the home view of the interface allows the user to select a specific component of the *Innohub* system for analysis. Once the component is identified via the search bar, the interface displays the number of CAPEC, CWE, and CVE entries associated with it. In the example shown, the selected component is the *Synthetic Data Generator*, for which the tool retrieves 4 CAPECs, 6 CWEs, and 94 CVEs. The user can then choose which category of threats to explore in more detail by selecting one of the three corresponding views – CAPEC, CWE, or CVE. Each view provides structured metadata for the selected entries, as illustrated in Figure 5.

For example, by selecting the CAPEC view, the interface displays the identified attack patterns as clickable buttons. Upon selecting a specific attack entry, the tool opens the corresponding documentation in the browser. To the right of each entry, three coloured labels indicate the typical severity level of the attack – if specified in the CAPEC database – using the following scale: Very High (VH), High (H), Medium (M), or None. In addition, the GUI presents detailed metadata associated with each CAPEC entry. This includes a description of the attack methodology and its targeted vulnerabilities, the potential consequences (impact), and the scope of the affected domains. Furthermore, it provides suggested mitigation strategies, such as recommended defensive measures and best practices, as well as references to related CWE entries that help contextualize the attack within broader vulnerability classes.

VI. EVALUATION

In this section, we evaluate the proposed framework with respect to its effectiveness, reasoning capabilities, and usability. Our evaluation is structured along two main

FIGURE 4. Home view of the *Risk Manager* GUI. The user selects a component (e.g., *Synthetic Data Generator*), and the system displays associated CAPEC, CWE, and CVE counts.

FIGURE 5. CAPEC view. The selected attack pattern (e.g., *CAPEC-57*) is expanded to show severity, impact, scope, mitigation, and linked CWE entries.

dimensions: (i) Ontology & reasoning validation, assessing correctness of the knowledge model and evaluating the application of SWRL rules and inference accuracy; (ii) Tool evaluation, focusing on performance and user interaction in the *Risk Manager* tool.

A. ONTOLOGY & REASONING EVALUATION

To assess the quality and adequacy of the developed ontology, we adopted a multi-faceted evaluation strategy

combining competency question validation, reasoning-based verification, and quantitative analysis. This evaluation aims to verify the ontology's capacity to support automated security validation, detect inconsistencies, and answer domain-relevant queries concerning the *Innohub* architecture and its associated threats.

1) COMPETENCY QUESTION VALIDATION

The ontology was initially designed around a set of competency questions, which define the types of queries

TABLE 5. Evaluation of competency questions with corresponding SPARQL fragments and expected outputs.

CQ ID	Objective	SPARQL Fragment (simplified)	Output Type
CQ1	Retrieve core architectural components	<code>SELECT ?component WHERE { ?component rdf:type sec:Component . }</code>	List of OWL Classes
CQ2	Find interaction between components	<code>SELECT ?c1 ?c2 WHERE { ?c1 sec:interact_with ?c2 . }</code>	Pairs of Components
CQ3	Get threats affecting a component	<code>SELECT ?threat WHERE { ?threat odtmb:hasTarget sec:SyntheticDataGenerator . }</code>	List of Threats Individuals
CQ4	Get threat impact and severity	<code>SELECT ?threat ?impact ?severity WHERE { ?threat sec:impact ?impact ; odtmb:hasSeverity ?severity . }</code>	Descriptive Threat Attributes
CQ5	Retrieve threats explicitly annotated with severity "Very High"	<code>SELECT ?t WHERE { ?t rdf:type sec:Threat ; odtmb:hasSeverity "Very High" . }</code>	List of Threats

the knowledge base should be able to answer. These CQs were introduced during the requirements phase (see Section IV) and encompass queries such as identifying the core components of the *Innohub*, understanding the core components of the platform (CQ1), how components interact within the infrastructure (CQ2), determining which security threats affect specific components (CQ3), analysing how these threats impact security properties (CQ4), and retrieving threats classified with “*Very High*” severity (CQ5). In this evaluation phase, we assess the ontology’s ability to effectively address these questions, thereby validating its intended functionality and completeness.

To this end, we formulated a set of SPARQL queries corresponding to each CQ and executed them against the instantiated KG. Table 5 summarises the results that confirm that the ontology meets its original design goals in terms of information retrieval, risk mapping, and compliance checking.

2) REASONING VALIDATION

To validate the ontology’s inferential capabilities, we executed the full set of SWRL rules described in Section IV-D using the Pellet reasoner. Each test aimed to verify the expected inferences resulting from core semantic rules encoded in the ontology, including threat classification, access control validation, and component-to-threat association.

The evaluation primarily focused on confirming the logical activation of each rule in realistic *Innohub* configurations. *Rule 0* was verified to correctly assert access permissions when token-based conditions were met, supporting the enforcement of RBAC policies in a formal and traceable manner. *Rules 1 to 3* were assessed by verifying their capacity to match the textual descriptions of CAPEC, CWE, and CVE entities against the technical specifications of system components. The expected inferences, specifically the links between external threats and internal modules, were successfully produced, demonstrating the effectiveness of the string-based matching mechanism. Furthermore, *Rules 4 and 5* extended this reasoning to alternative fields

such as notes and annotations, confirming the framework’s ability to capture less explicit threat descriptions.

To further evaluate the practical accuracy of the reasoning engine, we performed a comparative analysis between the threats inferred by the framework and expert-defined gold standards. For the following five representative components of the *Innohub* architecture, domain experts manually compiled comprehensive lists of relevant CAPEC, CWE, and CVE entries:

- *Identity & Access Management*: it manages user authentication and role-based access control, including permission assignment and enforcement.
- *Management DB*: it stores sensitive user data, encrypted secrets (e.g., passwords, API keys), and session information used by other components.
- *Anonymisation Tool*: it is used locally by members to anonymise datasets and machine learning models prior to sharing, ensuring privacy protection.
- *Model Marketplace*: it is a repository of pre-trained, anonymised machine/deep/federated learning models made available to users via a web interface.
- *Bias Assessment Tool*: it analyses datasets to detect and quantify potential biases, producing a bias score to inform data quality assessments.

These curated threat profiles served as gold standards against which the reasoning output was benchmarked.

The inferred threats were obtained by executing SPARQL queries over the KG after reasoning. To quantitatively assess the accuracy of the inferred threats compared to the expert-defined gold standards, we adopted standard evaluation metrics from information retrieval: *Precision*, *Recall*, and *F1-score* [45]. Precision measures the proportion of correctly inferred threat instances (true positives) among all threats inferred by the system (true positives and false positives), thus capturing the system’s selectivity. Recall evaluates the proportion of correctly inferred threats relative to the total number of relevant threats defined in the gold standard (true positives and false negatives), indicating the system’s completeness. The F1-score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, offering a single measure that balances both aspects. High precision indicates few false alarms,

while high recall reflects broad threat coverage; the F1-score provides a concise summary of overall performance in aligning with expert knowledge.

Table 6 summarises the performance across the analysed components. The results indicate that the SWRL-based reasoning rules exhibit varying degrees of alignment with expert-defined annotations. The *Bias Assessment Tool* shows the highest consistency across CAPEC and CWE, with F1-scores of 0.77 and 0.82, respectively. This suggests that the reasoning framework is particularly effective in capturing structured threat and weakness patterns within this component. However, its performance in identifying CVEs is markedly lower (F1-score of 0.21), pointing to limitations in rule expressiveness or in the ontological representation of known vulnerabilities.

Similarly, the *Identity & Access Management* and *Management DB* components generate moderate to high performance for CWE and CVE, with CVE recall consistently reaching 1.0. This indicates that while the rules are effective in retrieving relevant vulnerability instances, they often lack the specificity required for precise classification.

In contrast, the *Anonymisation Tool* and *Model Marketplace* components demonstrate relatively low precision across all taxonomies, especially in the CVE domain (0.14 and 0.09, respectively). This highlights the need for more granular and context-aware rule definitions in these areas.

Overall, the results validate the potential of SWRL-based reasoning for security threat inference. However, they also underscore the necessity of refining both the rule sets and the ontological coverage, particularly for complex or less-structured taxonomies such as CVE. While the framework exhibits high recall across most components, several high-priority vulnerabilities from the expert-defined gold standards were not inferred. For example, CAPEC-137 (Parameter Injection) was not detected in the *Model Marketplace*, despite the component's reliance on user input for model selection and download. Likewise, CWE-602 (Client-Side Enforcement of Server-Side Security), relevant to the *Identity & Access Management* component, was also missed.

Moreover, CWE-311 (Missing Encryption of Sensitive Data) was not identified for the *Anonymisation Tool*, although it handles sensitive information, possibly due to incomplete modelling of data encryption states. Similarly, CWE-79 (Cross-Site Scripting) and CAPEC-54 (Query System for Information) were not captured in components that process user-supplied content. These cases underscore the importance of contextual modelling and targeted rule refinement to improve inference precision.

B. TOOL EVALUATION

The *Risk Manager* was developed to address a practical need identified during the framework's design: enabling developers of individual components to inspect associated threats and vulnerabilities without requiring expertise in semantic technologies or SPARQL. To this end, a dedicated

interface was implemented to make the underlying knowledge accessible, actionable, and interpretable by non-expert users.

The GUI allows users to select a component from the *Innohub* architecture and presents a comprehensive overview of associated threats, based on CAPEC, CWE, and CVE taxonomies. Each threat is displayed with its severity level, impact, and suggested mitigation strategies, which are extracted from the KG. Filtering options enable users to narrow down the threat list based on severity, focusing on critical risks. This functionality supports security assessment tasks during development and integration phases by offering a clear and structured view of threat coverage.

To assess the usability, we conducted a small-scale user study involving 10 participants. The users were not familiar with SPARQL, but possessed general technical proficiency (e.g., system developers, DevOps engineers, or software architects). The study aimed to evaluate how effectively the interface supports interaction with the KG for threat assessment tasks. Participants were asked to perform basic tasks such as: (i) selecting a system component, (ii) reviewing its associated threats, (iii) filtering threats by severity, (iv) interpreting mitigation suggestions. Feedback from the study was highly positive. All users were able to successfully complete the tasks without external support, indicating a low barrier to entry and high learnability of the interface. Users particularly appreciated the clear presentation of information. Different suggestions emerged from the study:

- Users expressed interest in the ability to annotate components by linking new CAPEC, CWE, or CVE entries, along with justification notes.
- They also proposed the inclusion of a logbook feature, enabling them to record actions taken in response to detected threats (e.g., mitigation steps, design decisions), serving as an internal documentation aid.

Beyond usability, we also evaluated the efficiency and responsiveness of the *Risk Manager*. To this end, we measured the execution time required to retrieve and render information for each individual representing an *Innohub* component in the ontology. The application initializes the GUI in approximately 1.0 second, after which it executes SPARQL queries against the KG to retrieve and process data related to CWE, CAPEC, and CVE vulnerabilities. The execution flow includes semantic querying, result processing, and dynamic construction of the corresponding visual elements within the GUI. To evaluate average computation and rendering times, we automatically executed one query per component and calculated the mean durations for both data retrieval and visual display. As reported in Table 7, the average time per query is approximately 4.9 seconds for CWE data, 3.1 seconds for CAPEC data, and 0.5 seconds for CVE data. These values reflect the relative complexity of the SPARQL queries, particularly for CWEs and CAPECs. Despite relying on ontology-based reasoning and structured querying, the total end-to-end interaction time remains within acceptable limits for interactive use. On average, the application retrieves

TABLE 6. Performance of the ontology-based reasoning in identifying relevant threats across five system components. Metrics include Precision, Recall and F1-score computed separately for attack patterns (CAPEC), software weaknesses (CWE) and known vulnerabilities (CVE), using expert-defined gold standards as reference.

Component	CAPEC			CWE			CVE		
	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Anonymisation Tool	0.45	0.50	0.47	0.20	1.00	0.33	0.14	1.00	0.24
Bias Assessment Tool	0.75	0.80	0.77	0.88	0.78	0.82	0.12	0.88	0.21
Identity & Access Management	0.65	0.70	0.67	0.83	0.56	0.67	0.27	1.00	0.43
Management DB	0.60	0.65	0.62	0.83	0.50	0.62	0.31	1.00	0.47
Model Marketplace	0.30	0.35	0.32	0.09	0.64	0.15	0.09	1.00	0.17

TABLE 7. Average SPARQL query time and number of retrieved threats per Innohub component.

Threats	Avg Time (s)	Avg Results
CWE	4.9	38.6
CAPEC	3.1	27.8
CVE	0.5	63.8

38.6 CWE entries, 27.8 CAPEC entities and 63.8 CVEs per component.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a knowledge-driven framework for security validation and reasoning in modular systems. By integrating established threat taxonomies into a structured OWL ontology and implementing SWRL-based reasoning rules, we demonstrated how security requirements and vulnerabilities can be formalised, inferred, and interactively explored within a unified knowledge graph. The framework was instantiated in the context of the *Innohub* architecture, which was developed as part of a Horizon Europe project.

One of the core strengths of the proposed approach lies in its semantic expressiveness and extensibility. The two-part ontology effectively models both the system's architectural components and the associated threat space, while the reasoning rules enable automatic detection of vulnerabilities based on contextual metadata, access control logic, and threat descriptions. The inclusion of a GUI-based tool enhances accessibility, allowing developers without SPARQL expertise to inspect vulnerabilities, filter by severity, and view mitigation strategies. Usability testing with non-expert users confirmed that the GUI is both approachable and functionally effective, and user feedback suggested valuable directions for collaborative features.

The framework was validated using a combination of competency questions, formal reasoning verification, and comparative analysis against expert-defined gold standards. Evaluation metrics such as precision, recall, and F1-score confirmed that the system achieves high recall across multiple components and taxonomies, with particularly strong alignment for CAPEC and CWE entries.

Despite these strengths, several limitations emerged. First, the inference precision for CVE entities remains relatively low in some components, due to the ambiguity and variability

of free-text vulnerability descriptions. Second, the current rule set is deterministic and string-based, which limits its ability to generalise or capture implicit threat patterns. Third, while the *Risk Manager* supports rich threat inspection, it currently lacks collaborative features such as annotation, logging of remediation actions, or user feedback mechanisms.

As future work, we plan to address these limitations through multiple directions. We will enhance the reasoning engine by integrating probabilistic or fuzzy logic mechanisms to support partial matches and increase inference precision. Furthermore, we will extend the GUI with support for collaborative annotations, justification notes for new threat mappings, and an interactive audit trail. These annotations will be directly stored in the KG, enabling experts to create or refine links between components and security threats in a structured and persistent way. Finally, we plan to evaluate the system in other domains, such as industrial infrastructures, to validate its generalisability and operational impact.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. L. Martínez, M. G. Pérez, and A. Ruiz-Martínez, "A comprehensive model for securing sensitive patient data in a clinical scenario," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 137083–137098, 2023.
- [2] M. Narula, J. Meena, and D. K. Vishwakarma, "A comprehensive review on federated learning for data-sensitive application: Open issues & challenges," *Eng. Appl. Artif. Intell.*, vol. 133, Jul. 2024, Art. no. 108128.
- [3] F. Regazzoni et al., "SECURED for health: Scaling up privacy to enable the integration of the European health data space," in *Proc. Design, Autom. Test Eur. Conf. Exhib. (DATE)*, Valencia, Spain, Mar. 2024, pp. 1–4.
- [4] C. Sánchez-Zas, V. A. Villagrà, M. Vega-Barbas, X. Larriva-Novo, J. I. Moreno, and J. Berrocal, "Ontology-based approach to real-time risk management and cyber-situational awareness," *Future Gener. Comput. Syst.*, vol. 141, pp. 462–472, Apr. 2023.
- [5] C.-C. Huang, P.-Y. Huang, Y.-R. Kuo, G.-W. Wong, Y.-T. Huang, Y. S. Sun, and M. Chang Chen, "Building cybersecurity ontology for understanding and reasoning adversary tactics and techniques," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Big Data*, Osaka, Japan, S. Tsumoto, Y. Ohsawa, L. Chen, D. V. den Poel, X. Hu, Y. Motomura, T. Takagi, L. Wu, Y. Xie, A. Abe, and V. Raghavan, Eds., Dec. 2022, pp. 4266–4274.
- [6] S. Veronica, "Reasoning under threat: Symbolic and neural techniques for cybersecurity verification," 2025, *arXiv:2503.22755*.
- [7] V. Molnár, B. Graics, A. Vörös, S. Tonetta, L. Cristoforetti, G. Kimberly, P. Dyer, K. Giammarco, M. Koethe, J. Hester, J. Smith, and C. Grimm, "Towards the formal verification of SysML v2 models," in *Proc. ACM/IEEE 27th Int. Conf. Model Driven Eng. Lang. Syst.*, Linz, Austria, M. Wimmer, A. Egyed, B. Combemale, and M. Chechik, Eds., Sep. 2024, pp. 1086–1095.

- [8] L. Pandolfo, L. Pulina, and S. Vuotto, "SMT-based consistency checking of configuration-based components specifications," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 83718–83726, 2021.
- [9] R. Arp, B. Smith, and A. D. Spear, "What is an ontology?" in *Handbook on Ontologies* (International Handbooks on Information Systems), S. Staab and R. Studer, Eds., Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2015, pp. 1–17.
- [10] M. Vålja, F. Heiding, U. Franke, and R. Lagerström, "Automating threat modeling using an ontology framework," *Cybersecurity*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 19, Dec. 2020.
- [11] G. Antoniou and F. V. Harmelen, "Web ontology language (OWL)," in *Handbook Ontologies*, 2014, pp. 91–110.
- [12] J. Bao, P. F. Patel-Schneider, D. L. McGuinness, M. Y. Katz, and B. Motik. (Dec. 2012). *OWL 2 Web Ontology Language Document Overview (Second Edition)*. [Online]. Available: <http://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-overview/>
- [13] F. Baader, I. Horrocks, and U. Sattler, "Description logics," in *Handbook of Knowledge Representation* (Foundations of Artificial Intelligence), vol. 3, F. van Harmelen, V. Lifschitz, and B. W. Porter, Eds., Amsterdam, The Netherlands: Elsevier, 2009, pp. 135–179.
- [14] A. Hogan, E. Blomqvist, M. Cochez, C. d'Amato, G. de Melo, C. Gutierrez, S. Kirrane, J. E. L. Gayo, R. Navigli, S. Neumaier, A. N. Ngomo, A. Polleres, S. M. Rashid, A. Rula, L. Schmelzeisen, J. Sequeda, S. Staab, and A. Zimmermann, *Knowledge Graphs* (Synthesis Lectures on Data, Semantics, and Knowledge). San Rafael, CA, USA: Morgan & Claypool, 2021.
- [15] B. Parsia, "Querying the Web with SPARQL," in *Reasoning Web* (Lecture Notes in Computer Science), vol. 4126, P. Barahona, F. Bry, E. Franconi, N. Henze, and U. Sattler, Eds., Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2006, pp. 53–67.
- [16] O. Hartig, A. Seaborne, R. Taelman, G. Williams, and T. P. Tanon. (Jul. 2025). *SPARQL 1.2 Query Language*. World Wide Web Consortium. [Online]. Available: <https://www.w3.org/TR/2025/WD-sparql12-query-20250703/>
- [17] E. Sirin, B. Parsia, B. C. Grau, A. Kalyanpur, and Y. Katz, "Pellet: A practical OWL-DL reasoner," *J. Web Semantics*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 51–53, Jun. 2007.
- [18] B. Motik, R. Shearer, and I. Horrocks, "Hypertableau reasoning for description logics," *J. Artif. Intell. Res.*, vol. 36, pp. 165–228, Oct. 2009.
- [19] D. Tsarkov and I. Horrocks, "FaCT++ description logic reasoner: System description," in *Proc. 3rd Int. Joint Conf. Automated Reasoning*, vol. 4130, 2006, pp. 292–297.
- [20] I. Horrocks, P. F. Patel-Schneider, H. Boley, S. Tabet, B. Grosf, and M. Dean, "SWRL: A semantic Web rule language combining OWL and RuleML," *W3C Member Submission*, vol. 21, no. 79, pp. 1–31, 2004.
- [21] B. N. Grosf, I. Horrocks, R. Volz, and S. Decker, "Description logic programs: Combining logic programs with description logic," in *Proc. 12th Int. World Wide Web Conf.*, Budapest, Hungary, G. Hencsey, B. White, Y. R. Chen, L. Kovács, and S. Lawrence, Eds., May 2003, pp. 48–57.
- [22] U. Hustadt, B. Motik, and U. Sattler, "Data complexity of reasoning in very expressive description logics," in *Proc. 19th Int. Joint Conf. Artif. Intell.*, Edinburgh, Scotland, L. P. Kaelbling and A. Saffioti, Eds., Jul. 2005, pp. 466–471.
- [23] D. Granata and M. Rak, "Systematic analysis of automated threat modelling techniques: Comparison of open-source tools," *Softw. Quality J.*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 125–161, Mar. 2024.
- [24] N. Azam, L. Michala, S. Ansari, and N. B. Truong, "Data privacy threat modelling for autonomous systems: A survey from the GDPR's perspective," *IEEE Trans. Big Data*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 388–414, Apr. 2023.
- [25] M. Jbair, B. Ahmad, C. Maple, and R. Harrison, "Threat modelling for industrial cyber physical systems in the era of smart manufacturing," *Comput. Ind.*, vol. 137, May 2022, Art. no. 103611.
- [26] F. De Rosa, N. Maunero, P. Prinetto, F. Talentino, and M. Trussoni, "ThreMA: Ontology-based automated threat modeling for ICT infrastructures," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 116514–116526, 2022.
- [27] N. Shevchenko, T. A. Chick, P. O'Riordan, T. P. Scanlon, and C. Woody, "Threat modeling: A summary of available methods," Carnegie Mellon University, Pittsburgh, PA, USA, Tech. Rep., 2018, pp. 1–24.
- [28] Microsoft. (2022). *Getting Started With the Threat Modeling Tool*. Accessed: Mar. 14, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/security/develop/threat-modeling-tool-getting-started>
- [29] B. Schneier, "Features-attack trees-attack trees provide a formal, methodical way of describing the security of systems, based on varying attacks. Bruce shows how you can use them to improve security by," *Dr Dobbs's J.-Software Tools Prof. Programmer*, vol. 24, no. 12, pp. 21–31, 1999.
- [30] T. UcedaVelez and M. M. Morana, *Risk Centric Threat Modeling: Process for Attack Simulation and Threat Analysis*. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley, 2015.
- [31] EC-Council. (2024). *Cyber Threat Modeling (vast)*. Accessed: Mar. 14, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.eccouncil.org/threat-modeling/>
- [32] C. Alberts, S. Behrens, R. Pethia, and W. Wilson, "Operationally critical threat, asset, and vulnerability evaluation (OCTAVE) framework," Tech. Rep., 1999.
- [33] Cyral. (2024). *Threat Modeling with Dread*. Accessed: Mar. 14, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://cyral.com/glossary/threat-modeling-with-dread/>
- [34] LINDDUN. (2024). *Linddun Privacy Threat Modelling: Identify Privacy Threats in Software Systems*. Accessed: Mar. 14, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://linddun.org/threat-types/>
- [35] M. Frydman, G. Ruiz, E. Heymann, E. César, and B. P. Miller, "Automating risk analysis of software design models," *Sci. World J.*, vol. 2014, no. 1, pp. 1–12, 2014.
- [36] A. I. Brazhuk, "Security patterns based approach to automatically select mitigations in ontology-driven threat modelling," in *Open Semantic Technologies for Intelligent Systems (OSTIS)*, 2020, pp. 267–272. [Online]. Available: <https://libeloc.bsuir.by/bitstream/123456789/38619/1/BrazhukSecurity.pdf>
- [37] S. Manzoor, T. Vateva-Gurova, R. Trapero, and N. Suri, "Threat modeling the cloud: An ontology based approach," in *Information and Operational Technology Security Systems*, A. P. Fournaris, K. Lampropoulos, and E. Marín Tordera, Eds., Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2019, pp. 61–72.
- [38] A. Ekelhart, S. Fenz, M. D. Klemen, and E. R. Weippl, "Security ontology: Simulating threats to corporate assets," in *Information Systems Security*, A. Bagchi and V. Atluri, Eds., Berlin, Germany: Springer, 2006, pp. 249–259.
- [39] C. E. Landwehr, A. R. Bull, J. P. McDermott, and W. S. Choi, "A taxonomy of computer program security flaws," *ACM Comput. Surveys*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 211–254, Sep. 1994.
- [40] M. A. Musen, "The protégé project: A look back and a look forward," *AI Matters*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 4–12, Jun. 2015.
- [41] C. Golbreich, E. Wallace, and P. F. Patel-Schneider. (2009). *OWL 2 Web Ontology Language New Features and Rationale*. [Online]. Available: <http://www.w3.org/TR/2009/WD-owl2-new-features-20090611>
- [42] J.-B. Lamy, *Ontologies with Python: Programming OWL 2.0 Ontologies with Python and Owlready2*, 1st ed., Berkeley, CA, USA: Apress, 2020.
- [43] J. Brenner, "Iso 27001: Risk management and compliance," *Risk Manage.*, vol. 54, no. 1, p. 24, 2007.
- [44] A. Brazhuk and E. Olizarovich, "Format and usage model of security patterns in ontology-driven threat modelling," in *Proc. 18th Russian Conf. Artif. Intelligence*, Moscow, Russia. Berlin, Germany: Springer, Oct. 2020, pp. 382–392.
- [45] G. Hripcsak, "Agreement, the F-measure, and reliability in information retrieval," *J. Amer. Med. Inform. Assoc.*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 296–298, Jan. 2005.

LAURA PANDOLFO (Member, IEEE) is currently an Assistant Professor of computer science with the University of Sassari. Her research interests include artificial intelligence, knowledge representation, and reasoning techniques. She was involved as a Principal Investigator of a national project, while she participated in several European and national projects. She served on the organizing committees for several international scientific conferences and regularly participates in program committees and peer-reviewed activities for scientific articles proposed for publication in journals, international conferences, and workshops.

GIORGIO CORONA is currently a Junior Researcher of computer science with the University of Sassari. His research interests include the application of semantic web technologies and knowledge graphs to model and analyze data in the several application domains. He contributes to national and European research projects, collaborating with interdisciplinary teams.

DARIO GUIDOTTI (Member, IEEE) received the Ph.D. degree in computer science from the University of Genoa, in 2022. He is currently an Assistant Professor of computer science with the University of Sassari. His research interests include the modelling and verification of machine learning systems, with a focus on the evaluation of synthetic data and the reliability of neural networks in safety-critical domains, such as medical imaging, autonomous driving, and robotics. He has contributed to several European and national research projects and is actively involved in the scientific community, serving as a reviewer for international journals, participating in program committees, and contributing to the organization of international conferences in the field of artificial intelligence and data science.

LUCA PULINA (Member, IEEE) received the Ph.D. degree in computer engineering and robotics from the University of Genoa, Italy, in 2009. He is currently a Full Professor of computer science with the University of Sassari. His research interests include artificial intelligence, formal methods, and knowledge representation and reasoning. He has (co-)authored more than one hundred publications in peer-reviewed journals, international conferences, and workshops. He was involved as principal investigator of a regional project, while he participated in European and national projects. He served in the organizing and technical program committee for several international conferences.

...